

HANUMAN TEMPLE AT PAÑCHAKHOBALĀ, DISTRICT
PANCHMAHALS (GUJARĀT)

By

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Pañchakhobalā is located near village Desar which is well known for its Śiva temple. Desar is twenty kilometers from Champaner and is approached from Champaner via Dhankunna village on Champaner Udaipur road and Bhamariya. There is metalled road upto Bhamariya. The road beyond it is *Kachchha*. Desar is approached by Bus from Champaner during the fair weather. The temple of Hanumān is located approximately one kilōmeter East of Śiva temple at Desar.

The Hanumān temple is originally a Śiva temple. It consists of plan of a sanctum, an *antarāla* and a *sabhāmaṇḍapa* with three *arddhamaṇḍapas*, one each on either side and one in front. The sanctum measures internally 2.75 mts. × 2.45 mts. The *antarāla* measures internally 1.50 mts. × 2.25 mts. The *sabhāmaṇḍapa* measures 4.00 mts. × 4.00 mts. Each of the *arddhamaṇḍapas* measures 2.85 mts. × 1.70 mts. The temple is built of ashlar purple sandstone masonry and is very much weather worn. It faces East.

In elevation the temple shows from bottom upwards buried *bhīṭas*, *Jādyamba* decorated with lotus petals, *Karṇikā*, *grāsapaṭṭikā*, *rājasena* decorated with diamond designs and seated deities, *vedikā* embellished with standing deities and *apsaras* on projections and *vyālas* and ascetics in the recesses, *Kakṣasana* decorated with leaf designs surmounted by a row of geese, dwarf pillars with capitals, lintels and *chādyā* (PL-I). The roofs of the sanctum, *antarāla*, *sabhāmaṇḍapa* and *arddhamaṇḍapas* have collapsed and their ruins can be seen scattered around. Each of the three *arddhamaṇḍapas* is approached by a flight of steps. The temple is in a state of utter neglect and two thick trees have grown up inside the *Sabhāmaṇḍapa*.

The sanctum enshrines a *Śivaliṅga*. The interior of the walls of the sanctum is plain except a niche in the rear wall which is now lying vacant. The sanctum door-way is embellished with three *Śākhās*. The first *Śākhā* is decorated with stencilled foliage designs. The second *Śākhā* or the *rūpa-stambha* is embellished with a band of geese in the centre and with a *ghaṭa-pallava* at the top. The third *Śākhā* is plain. The lower portion of the door-way shows Gaṅgā standing in *tribhaṅga* on the right and Yamunā standing in *tribhaṅga* on the left. On one side of both the two-armed river Goddesses is carved a *Śaiva dvārapāla*, that on the right of Gaṅgā holding *triśūla* and *sarpa* and that on the left of Yamunā carrying *ḍamaru* and *khaṭvāṅga*.

The pillars of the *Sabhāmaṇḍapa* are decorated from bottom upwards with (1) *ghaṭapallava*, (2) leaf designs, (3) a median band of diamonds, (4) another band embellished with *Kīrttimukhas*, deer etc. The architraves of the ceilings of the *Sabhāmaṇḍapa* and *arddhamāṇḍapas* are decorated from bottom upwards with (1) stencilled foliage, (2) ascetics, acrobats performing *śīrśāsana*, trees, seated bulls, reading disciples, war-scenes, seated deities etc.

The door-sill of the sanctum door-way is carved with a *mandāraka* in the centre flanked on either side by a *Kīrttimukha*. On either side of the door-sill is shown a niche containing an image of a deity seated in *lalitāsana*, that on the right being Gaṇeśa and that on the left being Kubera.

Among the ruins lying around the temple, the following deserve mention:

1. A number of fragmentary pillars.
2. A lintel carved with a *Kīrttimukha* in the centre.
3. A marching elephant.
4. A four-armed male deity standing in *tribhaṅga* in a niche flanked on either side by a male attendant.
5. A niche containing an image of four armed Pārvaṭī seated in *lalitāsana* and carrying *varada* cum *akṣamālā*, *triśūla*, *sarpa* and *ghaṭa*. The niche is flanked on either side by a female *caurī*-bearer.
6. Capitals of pillars.
7. A bearded four-armed male deity seated in *padamāsana* and holding a staff in his lower right hand. The other attributes held by him are indistinct.
8. Three stone slabs each carved with a male warrior riding a horse.
9. Stone lintel carved with a *Kīrttimukha* in the centre and with a lotus on the other face.
10. A niche containing an image of four-armed dancing *Devī* and flanked on either side by a standing female attendant.
11. A Jaina Tirthaṅkara seated in *padmāsana* in *dhyānamudrā* in a niche decorated with a *makaratorāṇa*.
12. A stone slab carved with four flying *vidyādhari*s each holding a garland, two on each face.
13. A niche decorated with a *makaratorāṇa* and containing an image of a Jaina Tirthaṅkara seated in *padmāsana* in *dhyānamudrā*. On the left of the niche is shown a devotee in *añjalimudrā*.
14. Four-armed Māheśvarī seated in *padmāsana* on a bull and carrying *varada*-cum—*akṣamālā* in her only surviving lower right hand. She wears *Jaṭā-mukuṭa*, *Kuṇḍalas*, *vaikakṣaka*, *hāra*, *keyūras*, *valayas* and *nupuras*. Her *sāri* is fastened by a *mekhalā* with loops and tassels.

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Fig. 1
Hanumān temple—General view

Fig. 2
Hanumān temple, image of Hanūmān

15. A stone lintel carved with a *kīrttimukha* in the centre.

Besides, a number of architectural and sculptural components are lying inside the *sabhāmaṇḍapa*. The following are noteworthy :—

1. A ceiling slab carved with two lotuses.
2. A marching elephant.
3. Two elephants.

On the North-East corner inside the *Sabhāmaṇḍapa* is enshrined a modern image of Hanumān which is in active worship—(PL-II). As Hanumān is presently worshipped in this temple, it is known as Hanumān temple.

The *Jaṅghā* (Wall portion) of the sanctum is carved with a single band of sculptures of which the following alone are in their original position :—

1. A niche on the southern wall containing an image of four-armed *sarasvatī* playing on *Vīṇā*.
2. A bearded ascetic in *añjalimudrā*.
3. Four-armed Indra standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying *aṅkuśa* in his upper right hand.

The temple is datable to C. 11th century A.D. on the basis of architectural and sculptural styles. It is an important monument of the Solanki style of temple architecture of Gujarat.¹

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